

CURING THE CURRICULUM

Students' Take on Medical Education

Episode [11]: Form vs. feedback - from rituals to relationships in the clinic: Rola Ajjawi
#CTC11

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ABOUT THIS PODCAST

Curing the Curriculum is a student-led co-creation podcast that tries to bridge the research-to-practice gap in (medical) education. We aim to translate cutting-edge research into accessible conversations with actionable insights for students, educators, clinicians and anyone else interested.

TRANSCRIPT DISCLAIMER

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EPISODE TRANSCRIPT

Ulf Ebeling: Today on Curing the Curriculum, we're excited to chat with Professor Rola Ajjawi, a researcher and professor of medical education at the University of British Columbia in Canada. Rola started out as a physiotherapist and a clinical teacher before diving deep into how students and educators learn and communicate in clinical spaces. She's passionate about the powerful role emotions play in feedback, showing how they can both freeze us up or drive us to do better. Rola is all about creating learning environments where students feel they belong and can thrive. She's also the incoming editor-in-chief of Medical Education, the leading global journal in health professions education. Rola, welcome. And to start us off on maybe a lighter note, but directly into it, if you could give like a feedback superpower to clinicians and students, what would that be?

Rola Ajjawi: Wow, that is not an easy question to start off with. What would feedback superpower be? Can I have multiple superpowers?

Ulf Ebeling: Go for it.

Rola Ajjawi: Okay. I think one of them would be an ability to notice, to notice what what performance relevant information is available to us - all around us - that helps us make sense of how well we are going. That would be one thing. And then the second thing would be to allow ourselves to be more vulnerable, to ask questions, to say we don't know, to fail productively, and then to be able to have a conversation about that and to learn from that experience. And that doesn't stop even when you're a physician, as a professor, you know, I'm always learning with every paper I write, every study I do, every PhD student I work with. So it goes both ways. And there is a need to be vulnerable when you ask, how well am I doing? You know, how can I improve? How can we make this practice better? What does good look like here?

Ulf Ebeling: Interesting, because that's very different from how I as a student perceive feedback, because it's often a very sort of one-way street: you get told what went well, what could be improved and how. So why is this vulnerability aspect important?

Rola Ajjawi: Yeah, so we've moved away from the idea that feedback is one-way information transmission, although you see a lot of that practice still in universities where, you know, you submit an assignment and maybe like weeks later you get these comments and you're like, oh, what was that assignment about again? Oh, I don't know. I passed anyway. Who cares? And you just put it away and you never see it. And so, you know, the educator spent all this time writing this feedback and then the students, we don't know really, have they read it? Do they understand it? What sense do they make of it? Can they then use it to actually improve the work and therefore get better? And so we realized that this approach wasn't very relational. It wasn't very supportive. And really, it was just busy work for everyone. So we've been talking about feedback as a process, as it's about supporting learners to make sense of feedback, relevant information in order to learn and improve. That's the Molloy-Boud definition of feedback that we've also been working with. And you'll notice a few things about how we think about feedback now. It's about scaffolding learners so that it's about, well, what does the learner need here? What are their goals? How can we support them with that? It's about performance-relevant information. Performance-relevant information isn't just about what the teacher says. It's about what else, you know, how else, what other forms of performance-relevant information might there be. So if you're in a clinical setting, it might be patient outcomes it might be information from your peers it might be information from the nurses so there's a wealth of information that we take in every day that that makes us think about well how well am I doing? what does good look like? and so then you're developing your evaluative judgment and the last piece of that definition is around um the making sense of because we recognise that everyone interprets information in different ways and that we have to have a sense of the standard in order to interpret where we are in relation to the standard. And so that requires support as well and to know what good looks like and then in order to improve and to learn and develop. It's not as complicated as I've made it sound. As well, when you think about feedback as a process, it becomes about a relationship with someone too. So the relationship really matters in terms of how people make sense of

feedback information, how they use it, what they do with it. And it's not about just that feedback moment. It's about the setup before, the goal setting, then the, you know, might be that conversation and then what do they do afterwards? Do we give them another opportunity to resubmit an assignment or do we watch them with someone else and then we continue that journey? So it's a more, I guess, sophisticated, nuanced way of thinking about feedback.

Ulf Ebeling: Interesting. I recognize a few things, I think. When it's a feedback form I need to submit as a medical student, I do this on average about twice a week. It feels very transactional. You sometimes even have to beg your clinical supervisors to fill out this note. And I also feel like sometimes clinical supervisors can't be really bothered to fill it out. Or they ask you to write your own feedback first, and they just tick the boxes. There's this very interesting dynamic going on there, the sort of game you're playing with each other, sort of feedback tango you're dancing. So it sounds very interesting to move towards dialogue, to move towards the relational thing that lasts longer. And it does make sense, when I now reflect, I think about those conversations I've had with clinicians outside of the feedback requirements for the study, those conversations, when they have been good conversations, have been really transformative for me and my learning. So I appreciate those. But what does the science show us? Why should we move maybe towards this form of looking at feedback?

Rola Ajjawi: I mean, the whole thing in the way competency-based medical education was set up, it was somewhat in response to some needs around assessment, but also to formalise feedback because lots of people were saying, oh, I don't get any feedback. And so by... having these EPAs or whatever they are, then the idea was that a supervisor would observe the student performing and then would have a sense of how well they're doing. And then that would become a prompt for a feedback conversation. And the idea of documenting it means that there is a record and the learner might be able to go back to it and or it can be used for a more summative. Now the problem is when you make something a requirement and it becomes summative, then it actually foregrounds assessment of learning rather than assessment for learning. And so while they were meant to be low stakes, regular assessments rather than one high stakes one at the end, it still feels high stakes for learners. And as you say, then it just becomes this instrumental thing that we do just to tick a box. And so it undermines the whole purpose of for learning. So what I generally talk about is, and what the research shows is yes, there's a lot of gaming, there's a lot of instrumentalism, learners and educators don't really like it because it's an added burden, but there's potential to use those opportunities. The good supervisors will have a conversation as well that sits beside the form, not on the form, because you don't wanna put anything on the form that becomes public record either when someone is learning and developing. So as well, we see that there's some things that people just don't write on the form, even though they might raise it or they might just avoid it altogether. So the research shows that there are problems with that formal type of assessment and so a lot of my work has been focusing on how do we create feedback

cultures that foster those regular learning conversations, those informal everyday learning conversations. And that's a form of feedback. And we've started calling it feedback conversations or learning conversations to remove some of the baggage that people feel around formal feedback, where you get told that you're doing something good and something bad in a very ritualistic way.

Ulf Ebeling: Interesting. I would love to hear more about that and especially what that takes of people. And I also think what you mentioned is some things you don't want to put on paper. And I think that resonates with me at least, because it's really hard to be vulnerable on a form, but it's way easier when you have a face-to-face conversation. But so if we were to move towards this model, what does it take from maybe learners, from educators, from faculties? What's required to make this dream come true?

Rola Ajjawi: Ah, it's actually really, we've been trying to change practice and with variable success. Let me start broad and then I'll bring it back in. So one of the studies we've been doing is looking at feedback cultures and what do feedback cultures look like that are productive feedback cultures or just what do they look like? And so we compared ICU with surgery and we did it ethnographically. We went and observed where do learning conversations happen? What are they about? What are the silences? And it was really... they were more different than we had anticipated. So for example, in surgery, you have that time before the operation where there might be a bit of a conversation, maybe an opportunity to talk about who's doing what and the goals. Then when you're in surgery, there's this co-location with your supervisor. But what we saw is a lot of the feedback in surgery was a procedural skill. So where do you put your hands? How do you stand? What knots do you do? Because those are somewhat easier to talk about. So where the absences were, were to do with, like, aspects of communication or professionalism or the ward work. And that shows you what's privileged in surgery. It's the procedure. So why is that interesting? Well, I mean, it might not be interesting for everyone, but it's interesting to us because it shows how, embedded learning conversations are with what is valued in a particular specialty and that there are certain socio-material things that make it, that enable it to happen. So what do I mean by that? So for example, you know, that notion of performance relevant information - surgical trainees said they knew exactly where they stood with their surgeons. If the surgeon gave them the scalpel, then they could use that and that showed trust. And so that was a sign for them that they're doing well. If the patient did better and progressed as expected, that was a sign that they did well. Whereas when you compare that to ICU, so much performance relevant information is uncertain, like the patient could get better or die and it might not have to do with your clinical reasoning. There's so much uncertainty in that environment and very little feedback conversation because the way the timetables were structured, they just kept passing each other. They weren't together co-located at a moment where they could actually have a feedback conversation. So something about the environment, the spaces that are available, how the roster looks, even that you're together in a space at a particular time, those things start to tell us a little bit about a feedback culture and what is

valued and what isn't valued around what good looks like. We also did some work, ethnographic work in general practice, for example, and we found that there's a lot of parallel consulting. So the student would go and consult with a patient and then they'd come and talk with the GP. So the GP didn't see what the student was doing necessarily, but then they could talk about the clinical reasoning. And learners felt really comfortable to ask about the patient, but they never felt comfortable to ask, how well do you think I'm doing? Or what does good look like? This, again, implies what is sanctioned and what isn't sanctioned when it comes to conversations. And I think we need to open up the spaces more to enable conversations about what does good look like for this practice. So now what would a supervisor do? A supervisor can, for example, engage a learner in shared goals. What is your goal for today? You might say something like, I'm really interested in learning about X. And they might say, okay, we can do that. But also there might be some opportunities to do this other thing. So then there's a shared construction of goals. And then for example, you go see that patient, I'm gonna go see this, then we'll come back together here and revisit and have a conversation. So then there's shared activities. So then you might have a really quick conversation. How did it go? Oh, I thought that went well, you might try this or that or you know actually I think maybe you know did you notice this thing you know that's that that tells me that maybe they need something else you know so so there's something about also talking you through what you're what the supervisor told you through what they're noticing how they're making clinical decisions. That is also in a sense feedback and you check in on the goals. Okay, now that's a feedback loop closed. For the next session, I want you to try maybe having a history conversation in this way. Try these questions out. And then they do that and they come back at the end. Now that's in an ideal world, right? And actually one of my master's students did a study around goal-oriented feedback conversations. And what was curious with that Many supervisors think, oh, I've got to maybe establish a relationship first and then I can have difficult conversations. But what she showed is if you start with what's your goal, what would you like to achieve, and really getting the learner to think about what this relationship what this specialty can, what this placement can provide, that shows that you care and then the relationship unfolds more naturally. So the relationship, the bond, the working relationship you have with your supervisor that they show that they care, they're invested in your learning, We showed that students make really sophisticated credibility judgment about who they're willing to trust and who they're not willing to trust, who they're willing to ask, who they're not willing to ask. And they learn that through talking to previous students. They learn that through the hidden curriculum. You have a bad experience You go, OK, I'm not asking you any questions. And then you might use your peer network. That's also really important. And so if you're a super-, so I'll come to the learner's role in a second, but if you're a supervisor, it's kind of being aware that you have some power, right? And so by showing that you care, that you're invested in, that you're there learning, by setting up an environment that fosters regular feedback conversations, that will help strengthen the educational alliance and lead to learning. Now, for a learner, I acknowledge you're not in a position of power, okay? So, and sorry, so it's just, and one more thing about the supervisor, if you're willing to show

that you're vulnerable, you might say things like, oh, I made that mistake once and this is what I learned. So, you know, you just made a mistake. I did that as well and this is how I dealt with it. So you're kind of normalising this idea of, it's okay, this is what I learned from it, or I had this negative experience too, or, you know, I really, this is one thing I got taught and it's really valuable. So that ability to also share your own emotions, oh, that was really hard and that's why, but, you know, we have to understand the patient that they're coming from this perspective. Now for learners, There's this thing called feedback literacy and the researchers are really excited about this. I'm a bit more hesitant, but I think there is value. So feedback literacy is about helping learners develop their feedback literacy. What does that mean? It means that learners start to recognise that they have an active role to play that they need to be more active in seeking feedback, they need to be more active in engaging with it, in seeking performance relevant information from multiple people, not just their supervisors, in looking at others' practice and comparing their own and saying, ooh, I liked how they did that, maybe I'll try that next time. or maybe I need to learn about X and be prepared before the day before or whatever, or today didn't go well with this, maybe I need to practice that later. So there's an active role that is involved in feedback. And so your supervisor, you might not feel safe or willing to be vulnerable to seek feedback from your direct supervisor, in which case then you have to have maybe a network of peers in which you can discuss this with. We know that they, you know, spouses at home and partners are often a good source as well, but they might not have the evaluative judgment around technical expertise but they might allow for some debriefing to happen around the emotional and that sort of thing. So having a support network of peers that you can seek feedback from is also useful. But it's worth sometimes trying, you know, oh, I feel like I'd really like some feedback from you about how I'm communicating with a patient. So maybe if you have some trust, maybe having, or I want feedback about X or Y and really being quite active in asking that question. But I recognise that there is a power imbalance in that and you might not always be successful. So don't let that discourage you. And the thing about vulnerability and feedback is you have to be willing to say, actually, I don't know, or maybe acknowledge that maybe things didn't go as well as you had hoped or didn't go as expected or that you don't know how well you're going or what good looks like here. And that is intention with credibility. So when you allow yourself to be vulnerable within the world of medicine that assumes perfectionism, then maybe you might lose some credibility in the eyes of your supervisor. And so there's that tension as well. So that explains why sometimes you might not be willing to speak out or ask for feedback.

Ulf Ebeling: I also now, reflecting on this, tend to avoid this vulnerability because I'm more likely to say, oh, I know it or trying to sort of sneak my way through in order to get a good grade in the end on the feedback forms. In person, that might be a bit different, but it really depends on the relationship. I also really like what you said about goals, that goals can also open a conversation. Because what I found is we have to draft goals, learning goals for the internship before we start the internship. And I also tend to always write the same standard things I know they like to hear because it's really hard to know what a

department can offer before you've even seen the department or met the people there. So I think really discussing goals is beautiful because also a clinician can say, well, yeah, you can achieve this here or no, you can't, but maybe there's something else for you. I like that suggestion.

Rola Ajjawi: And it becomes tokenistic, right? You write your goals beforehand, there's a ritual, you know what they like to hear. But you're right, things don't unfold like it's expected, but also they change as the placement changes. So you need to constantly revisit them. And the learning can really only be scaffolded if you're working towards shared goals. Otherwise, they're making assumptions about what is important for you. And then you're clashing and then you're not interested and then And it spirals and it can really spiral quite quickly. Then supervisors sometimes make assumptions as well about how smart or how interested you are. And if you're not being proactive for any reason, then they go, oh, this person's not interested. But sometimes learners just don't want to be a burden, right? So we say to, you know, so learners also need to recognise that one of the things that a supervisor is looking for in a student is proactive, is that asking questions, being prepared, that sort of thing, which isn't always possible as well, but that... that is something that they're looking for, that sense of engagement.

Ulf Ebeling: Interesting. I come from a background where being quiet is a sign of respect and then now I'm in a context where being proactive is more actually valued.

Rola Ajjawi: And there is a critique, right? Like we sometimes conflate engagement with extroversion and it's like why does everyone have to be extroverted to appear engaged? it's not about just being loud, I think, but it's about showing that you are genuinely interested. And even if it's not the specialty you ever seek to think you're gonna be in, it's like, what can I get out of this learning experience that might help me as a doctor more broadly and might be just speaking to patients and learning to listen in a particular way, learning to notice in a particular way.

Ulf Ebeling: I agree. And I think those internships that are led like this by the clinician or educator are really beautiful, because no matter what you think about the specialty, you can learn a lot. Yeah. So you touched a few times a little bit on emotions. So what's the role of emotions in feedback?

Rola Ajjawi: They have a really strong role. So there's the emotions that we get as reactions from feedback with it, but then they actually shape what we do next. So emotions have a really important role in the work that they do. So for example, you might be with a supervisor and you might not feel a good sense of trust. And so then you might start to think, become afraid of looking stupid and then you might start to hide and disengage and then that kind of feeds off itself. So the educator also disengages because it's a relational thing. And then in the end, no one's learned anything and it's just been a waste of time and you've spent most of your time reading books or writing notes, you

know? So I think that they, by actually recognising, okay, something's going on here. I'm feeling like maybe I'm afraid to speak up. Should I check in and see, is this actually real or not? Maybe I could, ask a safe question, see how they respond and then move from there. But just being able to reflect on that in yourself and then putting in some strategies to go, ah, okay, so maybe I'm feeling fearful or I'm getting lots of, I'm anxious or stressed here. And sometimes also recognizing that discomfort is part of learning and that's okay. But then maybe something really critical happens and being able to debrief that is also really important so that the emotions don't continue to intensify. So I think there's things about the work that emotions do in terms of hampering learning or enabling learning, they have a really important role within that. And, of course, judgments can sometimes be emotions, like feelings. Like, you know, you make a judgment and someone goes, it's a gut judgment, and you're like, oh, I think that's kind of... No, that's what, you know, that's a diagnosis. And then you might actually go, why do I think that? So it's a similar sort of thing. They're kind of wrapped up together and emotions are really important for learning.

Ulf Ebeling: There's a lot of information in them.

Rola Ajjawi: Mm-hmm.

Ulf Ebeling: And it's about extracting that information. Very nice. I also think that if you have that relationship and that trust and the vulnerability that comes with it, then you can also more easily take negative... What you might call negative feedback, but really constructive, like you look at it in a more constructive way, right? If you feel like that clinician is really there to help you grow as a doctor rather than to give you a worse grade than another student next to you.

Rola Ajjawi: Yeah.

Ulf Ebeling: The perception changes.

Rola Ajjawi: Yeah. And so even if you think about it, it's about... improving the practice. How do I become a better doctor? Or even how do I reach a goal? Or how do we improve the practice together? They're all very different sets of goals. And you will be able to tell very quickly the supervisors that are really invested in your learning. And if it's not your supervisor, maybe it's a resident on the ward, maybe it's another, you know, peer so recognizing that learning happens in lots of different with lots of different people it's a social thing

Ulf Ebeling: I've come to think that you can never not learn i think we're constantly learning the question is are we learning the right things or we're learning also maybe wrong or harmful behaviors.

Rola Ajjawi: Yeah, and are we just learning to do the tests? Are we just learning to fill out the form in a way that is ritualised and putting goals that we know they want to hear versus actually really thinking about what are the goals I want to achieve and how might I go about doing that and is my supervisor in my corner? Or do I maybe need to, you know, there's a complex patient, maybe I need to debrief it with someone else before I do that with my supervisor. So it's kind of those strategies that help regulate what you're doing in the learning environment as well. But the supervisor has to come to the party as well.

Ulf Ebeling: And is it then also about the way you assess based on the feedback you've exchanged?

Rola Ajjawi: Assess what?

Ulf Ebeling: If you need to give a grade for an internship or on the student, right? In the end, it's all about grades, right? That's what we live for. A little bit, no. But so how do we do that then safely? Or do we need to get rid of grades and just enable feedback conversations? Do we need to get rid of portfolios? What do we need to do?

Rola Ajjawi: It's hard. We are actually, I mean, we've been thinking about grades and their role and there's a big ungrading movement at the moment. But, you know, that also comes with its own issues when you completely get rid of grades because they tend to determine the jobs and who goes where and also they also are a form of feedback if you think about performance relevant information as being a whole range of things. I think you can't escape, if grades are there, you can't escape the gamification that comes with them. But in saying that, a good supervisor can also help build the relational aspect such that there is the day-to-day learning conversations that happen alongside that. So unfortunately, there is a lot of learning for the assessment versus learning to become a good doctor. And the rationale is, well, I need to pass the assessment to ultimately become a doctor. So I'll just pass the assessment now and then I'll learn to be a good doctor. And the problem with that is that it's almost too late by then. You've not really worked out what your style is, how you want to present yourself, what sort of doctor you want to be with. I don't have an answer, to be honest. What we're doing in Canada in postgrad training, and I don't know if it's happening here, but ultimately progress is determined by a competency committee rather than an individual supervisor. So there's multiple opportunities for assessment that then get looked at by a progress committee. But unfortunately, some of that, what ends up happening is those people are the same people. And what they end up doing is just counting how many ticks you've got. So that isn't really the point. The point is that learners can show what they're capable of doing that is core to the profession. So I do think there is a post CBME that we need to really reflect on and think about within our contexts that are very competitive and to try and see other peers not as competition but actually as peers as other learners and to work together. But I do think grades kind of get in the way. In an ideal world, maybe I currently think that you would have something like not meeting standard and meeting standard.

And you have just those two things. And if you're not meeting standard then, or you're borderline, I mean, some people have borderline as a third category. Some people have exceeding standards as well, but I think it's really, it would need a culture shift, but it's how do we support the borderline not needing to really glow and to really improve and learn rather than stigmatising those students and there's a long way to go still with that. And we know that students who are different, who come from different backgrounds, who maybe look different, also get penalised and end up in because they're not like me. So assessment is a whole nother can of worms. What I would say though, I guess, is maybe we need to uncouple feedback from assessment. So feedback becomes the thing we do all the time to learn and improve rather than just justifying the grade. And if we can, grades or not grade, I'm not fussed, but let's just uncouple feedback from assessment.

Ulf Ebeling: Sounds very good. CBME being competency-based medical education. We love talking in abbreviations, but that's a very medical thing, not just the research thing. You also touched upon the different cultures and different departments, maybe the ICU, surgery, but there's many other examples probably. But you also, you've worked in Australia, now in Canada. you've seen the world, is this more or less the same globally? Or can we really learn from a certain region?

Rola Ajjawi: So I've worked in Australia, the UK and Canada. And in those countries, I can say, there's less country differences, that's the terrible wording, there's less cultural differences based on country than there is based on subspecialty. So there's a lot of similarities between those three countries. There are smaller differences, like I do think Canada is - there's more politeness which can undermine sometimes just being able to have a bold or difficult conversation. But I see more similarities across these three countries and more differences between feedback cultures in subspecialties. So really if you're in say one particular ward, it's about how do we get, enable a stronger feedback culture that is for learning for everyone. I'm not sure here what your reflections are on feedback in the Netherlands and whether it aligns with some of the work that I've shared already. But my reflection is there's more similarities than differences, recognizing of course that Australia and Canada are colonies of the UK and there's a lot of similarities in the curriculum. There's a lot of similarities in general.

Ulf Ebeling: Having read some of your research and now this conversation, I think it resonates very much. And I think it is very similar. And of course, culture can always offset certain things, but not completely. And I think also the specialty or subspecialty culture you mentioned, I think is part of the reason that Dr. Glaucomflecken, who makes these funny videos about the specialties, is known worldwide. And it rings true to almost everyone. So I think that that is just a culture of a subspecialty world-, more or less worldwide, probably. Lastly, you have quite a big job coming up. You are becoming editor-in-chief of the big journal Medical Education. And you're also then in a position to shape more the global conversation, how we talk about learning and medicine. So I was

wondering, do you have a vision on the future directions or questions that you will think will shape the next decades?

Rola Ajjawi: I think there's a lot of turbulence in the world in general at the moment. And, you know, like AI, for example, is just being embedded into lots of things, perhaps uncritically. You know, innovation as if you know just everything has to be new and it's that that's fundamentally better than anything that we had before for example so there's there's a lot of that hype that goes with technology and I think for me, we just need to remain really critical and really come back to what our values are. And I do think that education is fundamentally relational. And if we keep that front and centre, then we will do a better job. I think for the next 10 years, I'm really interested in the conversation around what is legitimate knowledge in medical education and whose knowledge matters more, science, art, how can we bring indigenous knowledges, how can we bring all of that to shape what a good doctor looks like, what good education looks like. So I want to have those conversations, but I want to have them critically to really be critical about what we're doing and why. So that really matters to me. But I think for me, the first year mainly is meeting the team, finding out what works for them, what doesn't, where the friction points are in the system, just settling into the processes first. Medical education is a journal with a long legacy. Like we hit 60 years in January. So I'm very cognizant of the responsibility and to keep that legacy and really just continue to strengthen. So it's a journal, what I'm saying is that it's a journal that works really well and it's more about then broadening scope and bringing more people into this conversation in a really rich, diverse, but critical and credible way.

Ulf Ebeling: I'm looking forward to reading all about that or hearing about it. I think we've learned a lot about emotions, feedback, assessment, I think many things to think about. Aside from maybe vulnerability, that's my main takeaway I think I need to reflect on as a learner. Do you have a last takeaway you would like to give to educators or learners or both?

Rola Ajjawi: My last takeaway is to say it's hard. I know it's hard. I avoid hard feedback conversations, but sometimes hard things are good for us. So, you know, having those bold conversations and being willing to speak up is important and it might be uncomfortable, but it's hopefully worth it.

Ulf Ebeling: Maybe we should just invite more feedback. So did you have any for me?

Rola Ajjawi: No.

Ulf Ebeling: No. OK. Or you're just avoiding it. We will never know. No. Well, thank you very much for joining us. It was a pleasure and honor. And I hope people can take something away from it.

Rola Ajjawi: Oh, I hope so too. Thank you.

Ulf Ebeling: Thank you.

END OF TRANSCRIPT